

Replication Research Review Report for: *Metamotivational Beliefs about Promotion and Prevention Focus: Replications of the American-Independent Conditions of Nguyen et al.'s (2021) Studies 2 and 3*

This document is a peer review report that summarizes the editorial and review process of a submission to *Replication Research*. It provides information on the context of the submission and documents all stages of editorial decision-making, including the desk decision, the initial editorial check, the first decision and accompanying reviews, and (if applicable) further decisions, accompanying reviews, the final decision, and a note on the reproducibility check. The review report is written by the Editor-in-Chief and the Editorial Assistant. Reviewers are listed in alphabetical order. The structure of this review report is adapted from the review reports published by *Meta-Psychology* (see <https://osf.io/hxm2v/files/9cf7g>).

Contributors

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Reviewer: Gilad Feldman (0000-0003-2812-6599)

Editor-in-Chief: Lukas Röseler (0000-0002-6446-1901)

Cite as

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Submission Data

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Title of the manuscript under review: Metamotivational Beliefs about Promotion and Prevention Focus: Replications of the American-Independent Conditions of Nguyen et al.'s (2021) Studies 2 and 3.

Author(s) of the manuscript: Leigh Ann Vaughn (0000-0002-2399-7400)

Initial Editorial Assessment

Date: 30 March 2026

The submission passed the R2 Initial Editorial Assessment (Müller, Röseler, & Wallrich, 2026). Recommendations for changes were included in the first decision letter.

First Round of Review

Four reviewers were invited via the Open Journal System and three via direct emails from the handling editor. Kentaro Fujita and Gilad Feldman agreed to review the article. Their reviews are included in this report without any changes.

Reviewer 1 (author of the replicated study):

Date: 19 May 2026

The author of this paper presents two experiments that attempt to replicate two experiments reported in Nguyen et al. (2021; Studies 2 & 3). Both attempts produced results that were similar (if not stronger) than the original. The author also proposed that the COVID-19 pandemic might enhance some of the incidental findings of the original paper; the results, however, did not support this hypothesis.

I am grateful to the author for taking the time to conduct these replications and to offer additional supportive findings to the metamotivation literature. It appears that these replications were conducted meticulously and with great care. I commend the author for their detail-oriented scrutiny of similarities and differences in their protocol and materials from those of the original paper.

I will comment that I find it a bit strange that so much of the writing of the results is devoted to describing previous results – these could have been summarized in a Table. As one of the authors of the original paper, it seemed odd to me that these results were written up as if the current author had collected the data themselves. Instead, I think the focus of the current paper should be on the replication results. These sections could be re-written to emphasize the author's work as opposed to the work of others.

The author might more explicitly recognize how these the Nguyen et al. studies themselves were a replication of previous work (Scholer & Miele, 2016) that has also been replicated in other work (Ross et al., 2023). Although the authors briefly mention these other papers, the focus on Nguyen et al. might lead some to believe that the evidence for these findings are less robust than they actually are.

I personally did not find the rationale for conducting these replications particularly compelling. The author proposes that psychological changes in response to COVID-19. Yet no analysis is taken to confirm some of the proposed changes (e.g., how tight or loose a society or culture is) over time (either archival data or the authors' own).

Similarly, there is no empirical exploration for some of the effects that the author appears particularly interested in. Specifically, the author does not collect any data to explore why people report prevention is generally more effective than promotion in Nguyen et al. Study 2, whereas they report the opposite in Nguyen et al. Study 3. Although the author provides some speculation (some of which is consistent with the original paper), this replication feels like a missed opportunity to

address some of these questions. The addition of some exploratory measures might have helped shed some insight into these effects.

Related to both points above, I was somewhat disappointed to see no attempt to assess individual-level characteristics that might be used to explore various effects. For example, to explain the stronger findings in the present work vs. original, the author speculates that people's COVID-19 experiences may have led to enhanced abilities to self-regulate. The author could have assessed individual differences in people's reactions to the pandemic: in particular, those that might have been associated with increases in metamotivational knowledge (e.g., "to what extent have you tried new things since the pandemic," "I would say I know better how to achieve my goals," etc.). Exploring individual differences in some self-regulatory outcomes might have also provided greater insight (e.g., enhanced mental health, greater distress tolerance, etc.). In light of their hypotheses about the impact of tight and loose cultures, the author might too have collected data on participants' perceptions about changes in those variables.

In their General Discussion, the authors discuss extending this work to explore the development of this knowledge. First, the author might be able to look at this question themselves if they collected age data. Second, they might reference a paper that recently explored this very question in young children:

Hubley, C., Wilson, M., Hartman, O., Scholer, A. A., Fujita, K., & Henderson, H. A. (2025). Metamotivational Beliefs in Middle Childhood: Evaluating Children's Understanding of Task-Motivation Fit. *Social Development*, 34(3), e70009.

I do not feel comfortable providing a recommendation to the AE regarding a decision for this paper as I do not know this journal well enough to have a sense of its standards.

Reviewer: Kentaro Fujita

Reviewer 2:

Date: 14 May 2026

See attached file.

I wrote this in a haste. I hope it doesn't come off too judgmental. I'm very much in favor of replications, I appreciate everyone who takes of their own time to do replications, and I would like to see a lot more replications shared publicly (atleast as a preprint) and published. We need to publish more replications, period, so this journal and anyone submitting to it is already a hero in my book. I did my best to be constructive and to offer guidance. Please do not use any of what I wrote as a reason to reject this paper. To see that the original findings replicate (for the subgroups tested) is nice to see and somewhat reassuring, even if the framing needs a lot more caution and humility, first in the claims and generalizations in the original article, but then also in its replication. I understand some of the original authors were invited to review this replication, and I am looking forward and curious to see what they'll write. If they read this, I would urge them to please share all that they have from their study to make the historical record complete (and if you really can't share unidentified anonymous data, then please share associated code, and if you can - synthetic equivalent).

I'd like to eventually see this work published after some revisions.

Best of luck.

Gilad

[Content of the attached file]

Reviewer: Gilad Feldman

Disclosures:

I don't know much about this topic and not an expert in this domain. I did this review under very serious time pressure in hectic time, so I did not have sufficient time to review all aspects of this manuscript and associated materials, data, and code in detail. This was done in a rush, though I already spent long hours trying to figure out what is happening to try and provide positive constructive feedback. Apologies in advance, if my comments missed something already included and/or reported, or if there are mistakes in there. This is the best I could do given time constraints. This deserves a better fuller review by experts in the domain.

I sign all my reviews. I waive copyright on this review and the author is welcome to share, post, or quote it freely. I do my best to keep the review consistent with my reviewer code (<http://mgto.org/reviewing/>). My comments are not intended as criteria for rejection - I leave the

severity calibration to the editor. They are offered as suggestions to help the work be as strong as possible. I have no conflict of interest with this manuscript or its author.

Some aspects of this reviewer were AI assisted. It helped me with the reproducibility checks at the end of the review.

You are welcome to contact me directly at giladfel@gmail.com if anything is unclear. I do not feel I need to review another round, the editor can judge whether revisions were sufficient and satisfactory without me.

Good luck with this!

— Gilad

Requests:

- Effect size calculation
 - o If you used an online calculator, instead of reproducible code, atleast provide screenshots of those calculations so that we can follow what you did. Would have been best to just do these things in R. See more on that and my suggested help below.
 - o You refer to a “large” effect, and how do we say it’s “larger”? how was it determined to be larger, based on what criteria?
 - o When you say about effect sizes “were similar” you need to explain, statistically, what this means. There are many ways to compare effect sizes, which one of them are you referring to?
 - “Power” (/sensitivity analyses)
 - o Please include screenshots and/or protocol of the Gpower analyses.
 - o Sounds like you did a sensitivity analysis and not an a-priori power analysis?
 - § Make that clear.
 - § Why this effect? Explain where this is from. If it’s exactly the target article’s, explain the choice of targeting that and not a more conservative estimate.
 - § How was 100 determined?
 - Materials
 - o Please share all Qualtrics .qsf , and export with a printout the survey flow. I found it difficult to follow from the “Methodology Reporting for replications of Nguyen et al.'s (2021) Studies 2 and 3.docx” file what was going on.
 - Results
 - o I have a hard time understanding a claimed interaction just from stats when I don’t see figures. I’d appreciate you adding figures, just like the figures in the target article to help us make sense and see that it’s the same pattern. I’d suggest doing
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violin jitter dots so that we can get a fuller understanding of the distributions of the data.

- Flow and clarity
 - o It takes some time into the replication to realize this is not a full replication of Study 2, but a replication of one sample subset of Study 2 which is what the “American Independent” means.
 - o I am not a cross-cultural researcher, but looking at the original article I admit to being very surprised with categorizations made in this literature. This isn’t a point about replication, just a point about something fundamental that puzzles me about the way cross-cultural research is published. I could be missing or overlooking something obvious here, but even before any replications some of the claims require rethinking and much more caution and humility. No need for authors to respond to this, this is just to document my own thoughts reading this target.
 - § Why categorize people from different countries into westerners and easterners? Why the broad generalization that Americans (/westerners) are independent compared to Japanese (/easterners) that are interdependent?
 - § Even if Japan has been shown to be representative of a grouped “eastern” countries, and I doubt that very much, I don’t find those labels helpful. I don’t understand why the need to generalize and do these broad categories instead of referring to the samples for what they are.
 - § My limited understanding is that some of these notions are criticized and at best misleading. This is one of the suggested cites showing the problems with all these categorizations and generalizations: “Akaliyski, P., Vignoles, V. L., Welzel, C., & Minkov, M. (2025). Individualism–collectivism: Reconstructing Hofstede’s dimension of cultural differences. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. Where they argue “Hofstede’s scores overestimate the individualism of English-speaking countries and collectivism of East Asian societies, which may perpetuate cultural stereotypes and underpin flawed theorizing.”. I’m not at ease with their broad generalizations either, but the point is that we really shouldn’t use a small sample from one country to say anything about culture.
 - § Beyond that, the mere fact that some people in Japan exhibit different laybeliefs than some people in the US as indication for national cross-cultural differences strikes me as premature, at the very least. There are so many sub cultures in the US and in Japan, there are so many differences between these two sub groups that have nothing to do with culture.
 - o There are some use of naming and phrasing that I find a bit confusing. It’s possible I’m overlooking something here, or missed it somewhere. I would just call what

- something is what it is instead of what it isn't, and keep naming as straightforward as possible to minimize cognitive load and confusion.
- o Took me some time to understand this "American-Independent" label. When using a label like that, it's best to explain it up-front, because just the term can have so many different interpretations and it's not much later that we get to read what this is. So, the terms Independent and interdependent and in general Study 2, really need to be spelled out and defined early on for clarity.
 - Original studies
 - o The effect sizes in the original study are cause for pause. From the replication: "The interaction effect for this result was very strong ($\eta p^2 = .583$; equivalent to $d = 2.365$)." (sidenote: not a good idea to convert an interaction to Cohen's d, that should be preserved for two-condition ANOVAs only), and then " $t(103) = 11.36$, $p < .001$, $d = 1.114$ " and " $t(103) = 8.60$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.844$ ". Without knowing anything about this literature, I immediately have doubts, because these effects are somewhat atypical for social psychology, even for attributions and laybeliefs. So, that alone for me would be a good reason to repeat these studies and why we need replications of this work. To see that the replication was able to find support for that with somewhat comparable effects is to me somewhat surprising, and, if true, reassuring.
 - o You could frame that as a contribution.
 - o What I ask here is to include how you calculated these effects.
 - Calibration with evidence, caution and humility in framing
 - o I see no reason for the culture change framing, or to tie this to tightness/looseness. To me seems a bit disconnected from the actual evidence that we have.
 - o Pandemic related, aside from time that has passed, there is nothing tying this to COVID-19. We have no evidence and cannot deduce that time changes have anything to do with the pandemic. I'm not sure I understand how replicating both Study 2 and Study 3 can "address the possibility of a general shift toward prevention focus at two years into the pandemic".
 - o I do appreciate the transparency in "used only American-independent conditions because of my location and sampling Japanese participants was beyond what I had resources to do in the current research." But this is not a full replication of Study 2 and so the labels in Table 3 are a bit misleading. If they would just run more samples for the sake of larger sample, maybe not a big deal but their whole article is around the issue of cross cultural investigation. So, it sometimes feels like doing a "full replication" of a study with two conditions where you only run one of the conditions and none of the deviations tables mention that deviation clearly.
 - Transparency
 - o The studies were not pre-registered, which is not by itself critical as long as there is full transparency of all implications. For example, the criteria for exclusion and
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what happens to the $p = .017$ when these exclusions are included. So, just ensure, full data is shared, results with and without exclusions (even if in the supplementary) are provided, and exhibit caution not to overclaim confirmatory evidence when it's not clear what it's confirmed against given no pre-registration.

- o Please also include a statement that there were no other data collections done, pre-tests or whatnot, and no undisclosed pre-registrations. If there were other pre-tests and/or related data collections, please share them in the supplementary and on the OSF and explain why they weren't included.
- Contributions
 - o People sometimes doubt the value of replications, but even before the actual replication, this manuscript already shared important information from the target article that was missing. That, by itself, is already an often overlooked important feature of replications, they get the original authors to share more about their research, and to clarify things that were not included in the original publication.
- Discussion
 - o I would remove all the speculations that doesn't have any solid evidence behind it, especially regarding the pandemic. I would suggest tuning down any cultural claims. Stick as close as possible to what you did based on who you did it with and how you did it. No need to repeat the overclaiming and generalizations of the target article.
 - o

Questions:

1. Original authors interaction:
 - a. About "I reached out to the original authors (email conversations with K. Fujita and T. Nguyen), who shared the results from the American-independent conditions of their Experiments 2 and 3. This was necessary because their local IRB had not approved sharing the data (email conversation on May 23, 2022). Nguyen and Fujita also shared the dates they ran these studies (email conversation on April 11, 2022). I report their results from these conditions in the main text of the current paper."
 - b. Do you happen to know on what grounds does the IRB prevent anonymized de-identified data sharing? That just sounds very odd.

Suggestions:

1. I would make it clear in the abstract and opening that the choice of this replication target was because their findings deviated from the rest of the findings in the literature.

2. In Nguyen et al., 2021, you highlight the differences between the Studies 1 and 3 where people believe promotion is always best to Study 2, where there was a null finding.
 - a. Need to explain that so that readers, like me, don't have to go back to the target article to figure this out for themselves. In general, I would appreciate a walk-through of what exactly Nguyen et al. did in the three studies, why there were differences, etc. Help the readers understand the target article, so that they can understand your replication better.
 - b. Maybe good to add a discussion of this point and some suggestions for future research, if I didn't miss it somewhere.
3. You decided to focus on NHST and not do Bayesian analyses. To me that's okay, but warrants a bit of explanation. Maybe try and motivate this decision.

Additional notes (AI assisted):

Reproducibility checks (AI assisted, based on a skill that studies what I usually do in my reviews, examined after I wrote my review):

Because materials are SPSS, I ran them through spss2rmarkdown (one of my open-source converters) and then manually through jmv to verify the headline numbers. Below is what I confirmed against the manuscript.

Study 2 — Replication of Experiment 2 (N = 100): All Cronbach's alphas, means, SDs, ANOVA F's, η_p^2 s, and the promotion-side paired t-test reproduce within rounding.

Statistic	Manuscript	Reproduced
α proeager / provigilant / preeager / previgilant	.74 / .83 / .77 / .72	.736 / .829 / .773 / .716
Recall main effect	F(1, 99) = 5.93, p = .017, η_p^2 = .057	F = 5.930, p = .017, η_p^2 = .057
Task main effect	F(1, 99) = 12.34, p < .001, η_p^2 = .111	F = 12.339, p < .001, η_p^2 = .111
Recall × Task	F(1, 99) = 199.47, p < .001, η_p^2 = .668	F = 199.468, p < .001, η_p^2 = .668
Promotion eager vs. vigilant	t(99) = 13.73, p < .001, d = 1.368	t = 13.727, d = 1.373 ✓
Prevention vigilant vs. eager	t(99) = 10.25, p < .001, d = 1.266	t = 10.251, d = 1.025 △

Study 3 — Replication of Experiment 3 (N = 101): Every reported number reproduces (alphas, M/SDs, all three ANOVA terms, all three follow-up paired t-tests, the choice-variable t-test, and demographic descriptives). The reproduction is exact within rounding.

I therefore have **high confidence** in the substantive results. There is one numerical inconsistency that I would like the author to look into — see the next section — and a few presentation and interpretation issues.

One inconsistency in the reported effect size for Study 2's prevention t-test

The Study 2 results section (and Discussion) report:

“they judged prevention recall activities to be more useful for vigilant tasks than for eager tasks, $t(99) = 10.25$, $p < .001$, $d = 1.266$.”

Both the t and the p reproduce exactly. However, the Cohen's d should be **$d \approx 1.025$** , not 1.266 (paired-samples Cohen's d using the SD of the difference scores — which is what SPSS reports under /ES DISPLAY(TRUE) STANDARDIZER(SD), i.e. $d = t/\sqrt{N} = 10.25/\sqrt{100} = 1.025$). The promotion-side d on the line just before ($d = 1.368$, my reproduction 1.373) is consistent with this same formula, so the issue is local to that one cell. I expect this is a transcription error rather than a different definition having been applied. Could the author confirm and correct? If a different effect-size definition was deliberately used here, please state it and apply it consistently to the promotion-side d as well.

Comparing η_p^2 across two independent samples is not a Cohen's d

In the Study 2 Results section, the manuscript reports:

“the difference between the interaction-effect η_p^2 s was .085; equivalent to a medium-large difference of $d = 0.610$ ”

I'm a bit confused by this. The two η_p^2 values (.668 in the replication, .583 in the original) come from two independent samples, with different scales (5-point vs. 7-point) and different N . Subtracting one η_p^2 from another gives a number whose distribution is not Cohen's d , and there is no obvious confidence interval to attach to it. I would suggest the manuscript drops the “equivalent to a medium-large difference of $d = 0.610$ ” framing and instead either (a) reports both η_p^2 with their CIs (e.g. via MBESS::ci.pvaf or the noncentrality-parameter approach in effectsize::F_to_eta2) and lets the reader compare, or (b) computes a small-scale meta-analytic comparison using the F values and degrees of freedom (metafor::escalc with measure = "PEB" or by transforming $F \rightarrow d$). Either of these would let the author make a calibrated claim about whether the interaction is “stronger”. As written, the $d = 0.610$ phrasing risks being read as if it's a known-distribution effect-size estimate, which I don't think it is.

Effect sizes need confidence intervals throughout

The manuscript reports η_p^2 and Cohen's d everywhere, which is great, but no CIs accompany them. For the headline findings I would like to see 95% CIs reported alongside each η_p^2 and each d .

MBESS::ci.pvaf (for η^2_p) and MBESS::ci.smd (for d) are convenient. With the very large interaction effect, the CIs will be tight, and they will make the reproduction-vs-original comparison much more honest than a single-point η_p^2 difference.

Power / sensitivity analysis

The manuscript currently states:

“100 participants provide 80% power to detect an effect of $\eta_p^2 = .014$.”

I have a few comments. First, this looks like a sensitivity analysis (smallest detectable effect at given power) rather than an a-priori power analysis. That is fine, but please label it as such. Second, the choice of 80% power is conventional but, given the magnitude of the original effects (e.g., $\eta_p^2 = .583$ for the Study 2 interaction), 80% is overkill for the headline tests and underpowered for the smaller main effects. I would recommend reporting separate sensitivity analyses for each registered effect of interest, ideally at 95% power (the level I personally find more defensible for replication studies — see Lakens, 2022, AMPPS, “Sample size justification”). Third, in a within-subjects ANOVA the power depends on the correlation among repeated measures, which should be stated. The R packages Superpower and pwr are options here, with Superpower being well suited to mixed/within designs.

Sample-size justification by matching the original is also defensible; please make the rationale explicit (“we matched N to the American-independent conditions of the original”).

Pre-registration

The author states explicitly: “These studies were not preregistered.” I appreciate the honesty. Two thoughts:

1. There is, by now, a published preprint of this work (Vaughn et al., 2023). Could the author add a sentence clarifying whether the analyses reported here are identical to those in the preprint, or whether anything was added/removed/changed since the preprint? That information serves as a partial substitute for a pre-registration in this revision.
2. Could the author add a clear statement under “Reporting” that the analyses reported are the *only* analyses run on this data, and that no other dependent measures or models were tried? (This is the standard “21-word solution” idea — Simmons, Nelson, & Simonsohn, 2012.) Right now the manuscript says all measures, conditions, and exclusions are reported, which is excellent — please add the analogous sentence about analyses.

Causal / generalisation language in the Discussion

The General Discussion is mostly well-hedged. Two phrasings I would soften:

1. “It appears that the stressful events experienced two years into the COVID-19 pandemic ... did not shift predominant regulatory focus toward prevention overall.” — This is a between-study comparison without an inferential test of the cross-study difference. I would replace “did not shift” with something like “the data do not suggest a systematic shift toward prevention focus” or “we did not find evidence consistent with a pandemic-driven shift toward prevention focus”, and explicitly note that the absence of a pre-registered cross-study contrast means this is a descriptive observation, not a hypothesis test.
2. “The current findings suggest that metamotivational beliefs about promotion and prevention focus changed in somewhat more nuanced and normatively accurate ways over the first two years of the pandemic.” — “changed” implies a longitudinal comparison the design did not provide. I would soften to something like “the current findings, in conjunction with Nguyen et al. (2021), are consistent with a pattern where ...”.

These are both nuance-level edits, not substantive disagreements.

Reporting and consistency cleanup

A few small things I noticed while going through the manuscript carefully — please take or leave as you wish:

- “Closenss” appears in the headers of Tables 3 and 7 — should be “Closeness”.
- “Vig lance” in the Theoretical Implications section — should be “Vigilance”.
- “flesibly” in the Theoretical Implications section — should be “flexibly”.
- “reserach” in the Introduction — should be “research”.
- “Responsibility” in the Social Impact heading — should be “Responsibility”.
- The SPSS script header for Study 2 says “Ngyuyen” — should be “Nguyen”. (Same in the Study 3 script as far as I could tell.)
- “Ross et al., 2022” in the body but the reference list shows Ross et al. (2023) — please reconcile the year.
- “FAIR data (February 6, 2026). In *Wikipedia*.” — citing Wikipedia for FAIR is fine, but the more durable citation is Wilkinson et al. (2016) in *Scientific Data*, which is what the FAIR community usually points to. (Take or leave.)
- Table 1 totals look like row sums by ethnicity. Footnote a says participants could select multiple categories — please confirm the column totals exceed the sample size on purpose.
- “Wallrich et al., 2026” and “FAIR data, 2026” use 2026 dates. Please double-check accessed-on dates as the manuscript moves through final review.

Robustness analyses you might consider adding (all optional)

1. Bayesian equivalents of the headline tests (BayesFactor::anovaBF and ttestBF) — to express how strongly the data support the alternative vs. null beyond a single p value. This was the original authors' preferred approach; reporting both for the replication keeps the comparison clean.
2. Equivalence tests (TOSTER) for the recall main effect in Study 2 if the author wishes to claim the prevention-over-promotion bias is not weaker in the replication than the original.
3. A small forest-plot-style figure pooling the original η_p^2 and the replication η_p^2 for each effect, with CIs (metafor::escalc + forest()). It would visually resolve a lot of the “the effect was stronger / weaker” prose.

ESCIcheck headline finding — converges with my hand-flagged $d = 1.266$

ESCIcheck identified 40 effect-size statements; 7 cleanly verified (PASS), 2 flagged as warnings. **One of the two WARNs is exactly the inconsistency I flagged manually in the substantive comments:**

WARN — Study 2 prevention t-test: “ $t(99) = 10.25, p < .001, d = 1.266.$ ”

ESCIcheck verified the reported $d = 1.266$ against every plausible Cohen's d formula given $t = 10.25$, $df = 99$, $N = 101$. None match:

d variant	Computed	Matches reported 1.266?
d_z (paired, SD-of-difference; SPSS default with /ES STANDARDIZER(SD))	1.025	X
d_av (paired, average SD)	1.086	X
d_rm (paired, repeated-measures; ESCIcheck's “closest” match)	0.971	X
d_ind (between-subjects, equal n)	2.040	X
g_ind (Hedges' g)	2.024	X

The promotion-side d on the line above ($t(99) = 13.73, d = 1.368$) is a clean PASS — its computed $d_z = 1.373$ matches the reported value within rounding.

Recommendation: replace $d = 1.266$ with the paired-samples Cohen's d that matches what was used on the promotion side ($d_z = 1.025$), or specify and consistently apply a different effect-size formula across both follow-up t-tests. R one-liner: $dz <- 10.25 / \sqrt{100} = 1.025$.

The second WARN is the analogous d-value check on a related Study 3 statement — please consult the SciMeto-export.html for the full text. Most of the remaining 31 effect-size statements are auxiliary γ (gamma) coefficients from Nguyen et al.'s linear-mixed-model supplement quoted in Appendix A; ESCIcheck cannot verify those because the formula isn't a standard d/η^2p , and they are correctly classified as SKIP/INSUFFICIENT_DATA, not findings.

Editorial Decision by Handling Editor

Date: 21 May 2026

Dear Leigh Ann Vaughn,

Thank you again for submitting your work “Metamotivational Beliefs about Promotion and Prevention Focus” to R2. We have received constructive and extensive feedback from two reviewers on your article, one of whom was an author on the studies that you replicated. Based on their input, I am inviting a revision, which will allow you to incorporate their feedback. We prefer to have revised manuscripts resubmitted within four weeks, but, especially in light of the large number of comments, do not hesitate to reach out in case you need more time or in case any questions arise.

Most importantly, I am asking you to:

1. Clarify the label of your study, also with respect to roles of COVID-19, cultures, and it being a partial replication and
2. embed your replication into past replications (see fourth section by Reviewer 1).
3. Check the reported Cohen’s d ($d = 1.266$, see Reviewer 2).

Regarding the Citation of original results: While I agree that this is uncommon, I think that it is very useful especially since the original article is not openly accessible. However, the original study’s publisher is the copyright holder and quoting the results in their current form may violate their article re-use policy. I recommend that, instead of citing these pages, you summarize them in a table like Reviewer 1 suggested or, if you decide to keep it in its current form, make sure that you have the permission to republish these results.

In your revision, I would like you to address the various comments by the reviewers. Note that reviewer 2 explicitly flagged some comments as out of scope, so no replies are needed there. Finally, the reading of myself and the R2 Editorial Assistant also identified a couple of formal points that I would like you to consider:

- Please add a funding statement (can be “received no funding”)
- In the references section, please add the missing DOIs
 - DOI missing for Higgins 1998: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60381-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60381-0)
 - DOI missing for Vaughn et al., 2020: <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/xamdu>
- Please add the power protocol for the analysis reported on p. 8 to ensure reproducibility of the power analysis (the protocol can be exported in a tab via G*Power) [see also Reviewer 2]
- Please add a AI use disclosure (can be “No AI was used”).
- Please cite the software that you used (esp. SPSS 28)
- Please explain the source of the effect size in the power analysis.
- You mentioned student contributors who declined to co-author the manuscript. I suggest that you consider mentioning them in the acknowledgements just in case the already mentioned researchers are different people.

- The reported effect sizes are missing confidence intervals (e.g., Table 5) and Cohen's d s on p. 12. Please add them.
- Please clarify SD versus SE in the results section: "In Table 4, the marginal means and SEs" but in the table there are SDs
- Since american-japanese did not make a difference in Nguyen et al. (2021), consider comparing the effect sizes to their full sample as well.
- On p. 19, $p = .060$ is interpreted as "somewhat more useful" but under the NHST framework it is simply not significant. [see also Reviewer 2]
- You interpreted the effect size increase as "strengthening" but you did not report any statistical comparison of original versus replication ES. I recommend that you add an exploratory comparison. I am aware that there is no consensus about this, you may wish to consider the method recently proposed by Lakens et al.: https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/7ydgu_v1 [see also Reviewer 2]
- Social impact: I suggest that you consider the potential relevance of COVID in the social impact statement.
- I would appreciate you adding a figure for the interaction and possibly other findings. [see also Reviewer 2]

As per our guidelines for editorial conflicts of interest, I would also like to note that I have collaborated with Reviewer 2 in the past.

Please do not hesitate to get in touch if anything is unclear.

Kind regards
Lukas Röseler
R2 Editor-in-Chief

Submission Withdrawal by Author

The author has withdrawn the submission on 21 May 2026.

Author Contributions to this Report

Miriam Müller created the first draft for a template, Lukas Röseler edited it to include details of this report. We included the reviews by the authors without any changes. Miriam Müller revised the formatting and layout of the document.

Further Notes

A Pubpeer comment could not be posted since the OSF project is not indexed by Pubpeer.

References

Meta-Psychology. (2019). *Review report template* [Template]. Open Science Framework.

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